

10 yr without any appreciable damage. Early rice varieties Bindeshwari, Chaite-2, and Chaite-4 had little or no disease.

In a survey of farmers' fields in Chitwan district (western BI-prone area) 9 Jun 1988, a low level of leaf BI and moderate level of neck BI were observed in rice variety CH-45, a popular early variety.

More than 100 mm rainfall occurred in May 1988, compared to less than 35 mm in May 1987. The rainfall also occurred more frequently. Thus, BI races able to attack the early varieties are prevalent in nature and cause serious yield losses in years of early rainfall. □

Isolation of *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae* with a semiselective medium (KBS)

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P. fuscovaginae, the causal agent of bacterial sheath brown rot of rice and first described in Japan, is now reported in several tropical countries (Burundi, Latin America, Madagascar).

Table 1. Composition of KBS medium.

Basal medium:	
Casamino acids (Difco)	20 g
Glycerol	15 ml
K ₂ HPO ₄	1.5 g
MgSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	1.5 g
Agar	15 g
Distilled water	1 l

pH 7.0-7.2 adjusted with NaOH before autoclaving for 15 min at 121°C.

Components added to the melted basal medium at 45°C:

Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (= Cetrime, Labosi)	5 ml of a distilled water stock solution (20 mg/ml)
Trimethoprim (Sigma)	20 mg
Penicillin G (Sigma)	50 mg
Bacitracin (Sigma)	20 mg
Cycloheximide (=Actidione, Labosi)	50 mg

The last 4 components were mixed in 4 ml of 70% ethanol.

Symptoms are similar to those produced by other pathogens: grain discoloration, sheath necrosis, and spikelet sterility.

Isolation of *P. fuscovaginae* is difficult, particularly on older or deteriorated samples, because of the presence of other bacteria commonly isolated from rice samples. We developed a semiselective medium (KBS) that can be used to isolate *P. fuscovaginae* on different rice samples.

Composition of the KBS medium is detailed in Table 1. Basal medium is King's medium B (KB), but the source of peptone has been changed. Proteose peptone n°3 is replaced by casamino acids. This is important because the pigment produced by some strains (particularly from Madagascar) fluoresced only weakly or not at all in ultraviolet light when bacterial growth occurred on KB medium containing proteose peptone n°3, bacto-peptone, or casitone (Difco).

Plating efficiencies of 4 reference strains of *P. fuscovaginae* on KBS medium ranged from 5 to 100% after 3

Table 2. Plating efficiency on KBS medium of *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae* from distilled water suspensions.

Strain	Source	Plating efficiency ^a (%)
GR 2	Madagascar	100 ^b
HMB 264	Burundi	100 ^b
6801	Japan	5
		60 ^c
BCE 32	Colombia	100 ^b

^a Plating efficiency = colony-forming units recovered on KBS + colony-forming units on KB × 100. ^b After 3 d incubation at 28°C. ^c After 6 d incubation at 28°C.

d of incubation, and from 60 to 100% after 6 d of incubation at 28 °C (Table 2). Other fluorescent pseudomonads and a few other bacterial species grew on KBS medium, but development of most saprophytic bacteria and fungi was inhibited.

We used different media to isolate *P. fuscovaginae* on several hundred rice samples. KBS medium was the most useful, especially when laboratory facilities are limited. □

Insect management

Morphometric comparison of stridulating organs of brown planthopper (BPH) infesting rice and *Leersia* grass

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BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) males and females communicate prior to copulation, by means of acoustic courtship signals emitted by specialized stridulating organs located at the junction of the metathorax and abdomen on each side of the body. Each organ comprises a sclerotized metacoxata and a petal-like abdominal sclerite extended in front of the third sternopleuron.

As a calling adult slightly vibrates its abdomen in a dorsoventral direction, the sclerite rubs against the top of the

coxata, emitting discrete sound pulses, or clicks. The wave patterns, pulse repetition frequencies, and sonic spectra of acoustic signals have been found to differ significantly in BPH infesting rice and BPH infesting the weed grass *Leersia hexandra* Swartz.

To find out why acoustic signals differ in the two populations, we compared the stridulating organs (length, width, number of chitinous scales on coxata and sclerite) of males and females from each population.

We used an aspirator to collect 20 brachypterous males and 20 females from a BPH population maintained on TN1 rice plants and from a population reared on *Leersia* plants. The insects were prepared for morphological examination as follows: 1) boil in 95% ethyl alcohol in a water bath for 5 min; 2) macerate in 10% lukewarm NaOH for 15 min; 3) wash with 95% ethyl alcohol and boil in chloral-phenol (1:1 part chloral hydrate and phenol crystals) for 20 min; 4) orient and mount left and